

TABLE 1

Aryl Group	R	m.p. °C
1. phenyl	H	170
2. <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	H	166
3. <i>p</i> -tolyl	H	208
4. <i>p</i> -anisyl	H	198
5. phenyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	170
6. <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	211
7. <i>p</i> -tolyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	190
8. <i>p</i> -anisyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	178

All melting points are uncorrected. Nitrogen analysis of all compounds was found to be satisfactory.

2-Arylamino-1, 3, 4-thiadiazolyl-5-thio-4'-carboxymethyl-2'-methyl-6' or 7' or 8' aryl substituted quinolines: The sodium salts of 2-arylamino-1, 3, 4-thiadiazole were treated with II (0.01 mole) in Na_2CO_3 solution (1.75 g in 10 ml water) and finally dimethyl formamide (10 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 hrs and cooled. It was then diluted with water and filtered. The filtrate was acidified with conc. HCl. The precipitate so obtained was washed well with water, dried and recrystallised from dilute methanol (Table 2). Compounds were obtained in 50-65% yields.

TABLE 2

Aryl group	R	m.p. °C
1. phenyl	H	198
2. <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	H	162
3. <i>p</i> -tolyl	H	178
4. <i>p</i> -anisyl	H	180
5. phenyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	196
6. <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	194
7. <i>p</i> -tolyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	212
8. <i>p</i> -anisyl	<i>o</i> -tolyl	220(d)

All melting points are uncorrected. Nitrogen analysis of all the compounds was found to be satisfactory.

Biological screening: Of the sixteen compounds synthesised, fifteen were tested against the axenic culture of *E. histolytica* at a concentration of 62.5 $\mu\text{g/ml}$. None of the compounds was found to possess any significant amoebicidal activity.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the Head of Chemistry Department for necessary facilities and Dr. Nitya Nand, Director, C. D. R. I., Lucknow for analytical and biological screening of the compounds. One of them (P. S.) is grateful to the C. S. I. R., New Delhi for a Junior Research Fellowship.

References

- V. S. MISRA and V. K. SAXENA *J. Prakt. Chemie*, 1972, 314, 958.
- V. S. MISRA and V. K. SAXENA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, 51, 967.
- V. S. MISRA and V. K. SAXENA, *Pol. J. Pharmacol. Pharm.*, 1975, 27, 589.
- E. MASSARINI, D. NARDI, S. ROSSI, A. TAJANA and A. DEGANI, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1971, 14, 635.
- M. NAKANISHI, Japan Pat. 68, 13,468, *Chem. Abs.*, 1969, 70, 1971.
- A. R. SURREY and T. R. MAYER, *J. Med. Pharm. Chem.*, 1961, 3, 409, 419.
- O. K. YOUNG, D. E. MAHONYANDI, W. WHITE HOUSE, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1971, 60, 386.
- C. SINGH and C. N. KACHRU, *Indian J. Appl. Chem*, 1971, 34, 137, 273.
- V. S. MISRA and SHAKUNTALA AGARWAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, 56, 175.
- T. CEBALO, Ger. Patent., 1971, 2050979, *Chem. Abs.*, 1971, 75, 49094.
- I. AOKI, Japan Patent, 1970, 7028373.
- A. B. SEN and S. K. GUPTA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 39, 629.
- R. P. RAO and J. N. SINGH, *Vigyan Parishad Anusandhan Patrika*, 1973, 16, 73.
- R. P. RAO and ABDUL WAHAB, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, 55, 389.
- V. K. MEHTA and S. R. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1966, 43, 235.
- V. K. MEHTA and S. R. PATEL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1968, 45, 633.
- A. K. SEN GUPTA and A. K. RAMRAKHYANI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1973, 50, 742.

Anti-Inflammatory and Anti-Proteolytic Activity of Some Newly Synthesized Phenothiazine Derivatives

M. VERMA*, V. R. GUJRATI, A. K. SAXENA

and

K. SHANKER**

Department of Pharmacology and Therapeutics, King George's Medical College, Lucknow-226 003

Manuscript received 15 November 1980, revised 5 June 1981.
accepted 31 August 1981

PHENOTHIAZINE derivatives exhibit a variety of biological activities and are used clinically as tranquillizer¹ and anti-histaminics². Anti-inflammatory activity has been reported in metiazinic acid³ (10-methyl phenothiazine-2-acetic acid) and several substituted piperidine-phenothiazines⁴. Moreover, the anti-inflammatory activity of piperazines and piperidines is well documented^{5,6}.

Fourteen new substituted phenothiazines linked with piperazines and morpholines were synthesized and evaluated for their anti-inflammatory activity. Since proteolytic enzymes⁷ have been shown to play an important role in the process of inflammation, the compounds were also studied for their anti-proteolytic activity.

* Part of the work will be incorporated in Ph.D. thesis of M. Verma.

** For correspondence.

TABLE 1—10-SUBSTITUTED ACETYL PHENOTHIAZINES

Compd. No.	NR	m.p. °C	Yield %	Recryst solvent	Anti-proteolytic activity %inhibition	Anti-inflammatory activity %inhibition
1		72	56	B	56.53	Nil
2		82	60	B	73.98	14.14
3		101	60	B	58.83	Nil
4		132	65	A-B	54.00	Nil
5		70	65	B	62.00	5.04
6		94	55	A-B	59.00	5.05
7		122	60	A-B	66.00	Nil
8		246	65	C	65.22	Nil
9		208	60	C	62.32	Nil
10		216	60	C	66.67	Nil
11		232	60	C	57.98	Nil
		224	65	C	69.57	6.06
13		110	65	A-B	79.42	11.11
		163	66	A-B	61.00	Nil

A—Benzene ; B—Petroleum ether ; C—Ethanol.

All the compounds were analysed for nitrogen and the analysis was found within the limit ($\pm 0.4\%$). Experiments were done in duplicate and the results are the mean of two values.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. All the compounds were routinely checked by tlc on silica gel G. Infrared spectrum was recorded on Perkin-Elmer Infracord in KBr pellets. 10-Chloroacetyl phenothiazines⁸, 4-(*p*-aminophenyl)-4-substituted phenyl-piperazines^{9a, 9b}, 1-(*p*-aminophenyl) morpholine¹⁰ were prepared following reported methods.

10-Substituted acetyl phenothiazines : A mixture of 10-chloroacetyl phenothiazine (0.01 mole), substituted piperidine (0.01 mole) and triethylamine (0.01 mole) was refluxed in benzene (60 ml dry) for

20 hrs. The reaction mixture was filtered hot and the benzene was distilled off from the filtrate. A crude solid was obtained which was crystallised from appropriate solvent. The physical data of all these compounds are given in Table 1. Compound 2 in Table 1 showed characteristic carbonyl ($>C=O$) band at 1660 in the ir spectrum.

Biological activities :

Biochemical study : The anti-proteolytic activity of all the compounds was determined by the spectrophotometric method¹¹ by determining their ability to inhibit trypsin induced hydrolysis of Bovine serum albumin (BSA).

The reaction mixture, in a final volume of 1.0 ml, consisted of 0.05 M phosphate buffer (pH 8.2), 75 µg of trypsin (Sigma), 3.5×10^{-5} M BSA (substrate), glass distilled water and an appropriate amount of the compound to be tested. The compounds were dissolved in dimethyl formamide (DMF) and were tested at a final concentration of 5×10^{-4} M. The test compounds were preincubated with trypsin for 10 mins prior to the addition of BSA. After incubating for 5 mins the reaction was stopped by the addition of trichloroacetic acid (0.5 ml, 15% w/v). The acid soluble products of protein catabolism obtained after centrifugation were determined by the method of Lowry *et al*¹².

Pharmacological study: Anti-inflammatory activity of all the compounds was assessed against carrageenin induced oedema in rats following the method of Winter *et al*¹³.

Results and Discussion

All the compounds were tested for anti-proteolytic activity at 5×10^{-4} M concentration and the percent inhibitions are given in Table 1. An examination of anti-proteolytic activity in relation to the chemical structure revealed that various substituents at N' position of phenothiazine nucleus showed varying effects on activity. Substituted aminophenyl piperazine, aminophenyl morpholine, pyrrolidine showed better inhibition as compared to 4-amino morpholine, homopiperidine and substituted piperidine substituents at this position.

Maximum anti-proteolytic activity was observed in compound 13 in which there is 4-aminophenyl morpholine substituent at N' position of phenothiazine nucleus.

All the compounds were tested for their anti-inflammatory activity at a dose of 50 mg/kg administered orally (p. o.). Only five compounds (2, 5, 6, 12 and 13) inhibited the oedema formation. Their inhibitory activity ranged from 5.04-14.14% while other compounds had no effect.

The results of the present study show that the phenothiazines of the present series possess potent anti-proteolytic activity but poor anti-inflammatory activity. These findings, therefore, contradict the importance of proteolytic enzymes in acute phase of inflammation.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to Prof. K. P. Bhargava for his advise and encouragement.

References

1. J. W. DUNDEE, J. MOORE, W. J. LOVE, R. M. NICHOLL and R. S. J. CLARKE, *Br. J. Anaesth.*, 1965, 37, 332.
2. C. D. WOOD and A. GRAYBIEL, *A. Clin. Pharmac. Ther.*, 1970, 11, 621.
3. M. MESSER, D. FARGE, J. O. GUYONNET, C. JEANMANT and L. JULOU, *Arzneim Forsch.*, 1969, 19, 1198.
4. G. D. SEARLE and Co., *Brit.*, 1960, 880, 709.

5. R. P. MULL, C. TANNENBAUM, M. R. DAPERO, M. BERNIER, W. YOST and G. DESTERVENIS, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1965, 8, 332.
6. M. D. DRAPER, F. J. PETRACEK, K. W. KLOHS, D. A. MCCLURE, L. LEVY and O. N. RE, *Arzneim Forsch.*, 1972, 22, 1803.
7. H. BOSTROM, K. BERNSTEN and M. W. WHITEHOUSE, *Biochem. Pharmac.*, 1964, 13, 413.
8. T. ESTRAND, *Acta Chem. Scand.*, 1949, 3, 302.
9. (a) M. DUBEY, V. K. VERMA, K. SHANKER, J. N. SINHA, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. KISHORE, *Pharmazie*, 1978, 33, 10.
(b) E. A. CONROY, U. S. Pat. 2663706, *Chem. Abs.*, 1955, 49, 4730b.
10. M. J. KALM, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 7, 427.
11. V. KISHORE, S. KUMAR, S. S. PARMAR and V. J. STENBERG, *Res. Comm. Chem. Path. Pharmacol.*, 1975, 11, 581.
12. O. H. LOWRY, F. A. L. ROSEBROUGH and R. J. RANDALL, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1951, 193, 265.
13. C. A. WINTER, E. A. RISLEY and G. W. NUSS, *Proc. Soc. Exp. Biol.*, New York, 1962, 111, 544.

Chemical Constituents of *Viburnum cotinifolium* (Fam : Caprifoliaceae)

P. L. MAJUMDER* and (MISS) ANASUA BAGCHI

Department of Chemistry, University College of Science,
Calcutta-700 009

Manuscript received 28 October 1980, accepted 14 September 1981

THE medicinal properties¹ of the plants of the genus *Viburnum* prompted us to chemically investigate *Viburnum cotinifolium*, on which there is no report of previous work. This has resulted in the isolation of two triterpenoids. One of these, C₃₀H₄₈O₃ (M⁺456), m.p. 285°, [α]_D+70° (CHCl₃) is a triterpenic acid which forms a methyl ester, C₃₁H₅₀O₃ (M⁺470), m.p. 168°, [α]_D+58° (CHCl₃), with diazomethane and a monoacetate, C₃₂H₅₀O₄ (M⁺498), m.p. 290°, [α]_D+70° (CHCl₃), with Ac₂O/py. It was identified as ursolic acid by direct comparison of the compound and its above derivatives with the respective authentic samples. The other compound, C₃₀H₅₀O₃ (M⁺442), m.p. 215°, [α]_D+65.3° (CHCl₃), is a triterpenediol which forms a diacetate, C₃₄H₅₄O₄ (M⁺526), m.p. 151° with Ac₂O/py. The physical constants and the spectral (ir, ¹H nmr and mass) data of the compound and its diacetyl derivative are indicative of an uvaol² structure for it. This was confirmed by establishing the identity of the compound with the LAH reduction product of the methyl ester of the congener triterpenic acid.

A further evidence confirming the ursane skeleton of the two triterpenoids was provided by a comparison of the ¹³C nmr spectral data of the diacetyl derivative of the triterpene-diol with those of erythrodiol diacetate prepared from an authentic sample of oleanolic acid. The carbon chemical shifts of the two compounds differ significantly in respect of their C-11, C-12, C-13, C-27 and the carbons concerning their ring E, while the remaining carbon atoms have almost identical δ_c values. Thus, the signals for C-11, C-13, C-19, C-21,